

ISic1625

I.Sicily inscription 1625

Language

NeoPunic

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Aegusa, Aegates Islands

Place of origin (modern)

Favignana

Provenance

cave wall

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Favignana, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645077

Bibliography

Bisi, A.M. 1969. Iscrizione neo-punica inedita da Favignana. *AION*. 19: 555-558.

Teixidor, J. 1986. Bulletin d'épigraphie sémitique. Paris. *At* (1972) no.136

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